

ASPECTS REGARDING THE EMPLOYEES BENEFITS IN THE POST-PANDEMIC REALITY

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Abstract

Purpose – *The purpose of this paper is to present the local trends and evolution of the extra-salary benefits market in Romania in the post-pandemic economy.*

Methodology/approach – *We organized a study on major players in different economic sectors. The data is collected from employers mostly from the private sector. We analyzed the data in perspective of official numbers from the National Institute of Statistics of Romania.*

Findings – *In this paper we present the latest trends in the field of extra-salary benefits market at national level, in Romania in the post-pandemic economy.*

Research limitations/implications – *The data reflects information at national level, in Romania, mainly from employers acting in the private sector in various industries.*

Practical implications – *The results presented in this paper can be actively used in adapting the extra-salary benefits by interested users and it represents a radiography of the trends brought in the post-pandemic economy regarding the employee's appreciation of extra-salary benefits in Romania.*

Originality/value – *The results of this paper can be guide for any actors involved in the elaboration of the human resource management strategy for short and mid-term from small, medium companies and NGO's to branches of multinational holdings acting in this market.*

Key words: *Economy, Workforce Trends, Human Resource Management, Benefits, Great Resignation*

Introduction

The global challenges brought by the 2020 Covid-pandemic deeply changed the social context all over the world. Habits, social conventions and routines are changing, and these changes have direct impact on the way of understanding the way we work.

Multiple causes with direct interaction or not shape the way people report themselves to their professional activity as employers or employees. From social distancing during the pandemic to social unrest, from global record inflation to the highest rate of digitalization and automation, from security concerns in Eastern Europe to the polarization of the societies, governments are facing new challenges and take actions in modifying the taxation systems, entrepreneurs are struggling to survive in a high rate changing environment and employees change their habits and their relation to the employing institution.

In the struggle to keep the best performers and reduce the personnel fluctuation, business owners and human resource managers allocate special attention to the extra-salary benefits.

Major social phenomenon as “the great resignation” (Serenko A.) or “the great reset” are already highly studied and shape our modern world.

A fierce competition to ensure high performing key persons in the companies has started long time ago. In these challenging times, the competition only becomes more intense. Hybrid work, office work versus remote work offers a new range of possibilities and also challenges. Workplaces have changed completely, and a lot of barriers were removed. Work is now result oriented, not volume oriented, especially in the office jobs.

Donald Sull et al present in the paper “Toxic culture is driving the great resignation” published in MIT Sloan Management Review, 2022 that “More than 40% of all employees were thinking about leaving their jobs at the beginning of 2021, and as the year went on, workers quit in unprecedented numbers. Between April and September 2021, more than 24 million American employees left their jobs, an all-time record. As the Great Resignation rolls on, business leaders are struggling to make sense of the factors driving the mass exodus. More importantly, they are looking for ways to hold on to valued employees...The Great Resignation is affecting blue-collar and white-collar sectors with equal force. Some of the hardest hit industries — apparel retail, fast food, and specialty retail — employ the highest percentage of blue-collar workers among all industries we studied. Management consulting, in contrast, had the second-highest attrition rate but also employs the largest percentage of white-collar professionals of any Culture 500 industry. Enterprise software, which also suffered high churn, employs the highest percentage of engineering and technical employees.”

The 2021 Work Trend Index: Annual Report published by Microsoft shows that “41% of employees are considering leaving their current employer this year and 46% say they’re likely to move because they can now work remotely” and George Anders, Senior Editor-at-Large at LinkedIn says, “Remote work and migration patterns open up so many interesting jobs to people who may otherwise have had a hard time gaining access to them.” So, as boundaries fall apart, new opportunities appear for high potentials, and stability becomes a great challenge for employers.

In this context, one of the differentiators for keeping the staff turnover under control is the benefits package that could make employees decide to keep their loyalty for the company and have productive results.

Methodology and Analysis

The research was conducted by analyzing an employer benefits platform that gathers 20k companies with over 900k employees that delivers benefits from an ecosystem of over 65k partners that offer their services on the platform, mainly to private employers. Some of the presented output represent the results of mixed data sources, both from benefits platforms and official data from National Institute of Statistics in Romania.

We focus on presenting trends and decisions made by employers and consumers/employees regarding flexible benefits. In order to reveal the trends and highlight the different approaches, we excluded fix benefits like meal vouchers.

Our first result reflects the value of extra-salary benefits in Romania, which has an increase of budgets of almost 95% over the last five years. This significant increase reflects the importance of the impact on HR budgets with benefits. Because of the inflation and continues pressure for increasing the wages, employers look to the alternative of benefits, especially because of the economic benefits to the company, due to certain tax exemptions.

Furthermore, in 2022, industries like services and IT, have the highest benefits budgets per employee with 7.8% above the average, while in retail and production have lower budgets for employee benefits, as shown in figure 1. “Benefits budget sector variations from average per industry in 2021” in Romania based on platform data.

While taking into consideration industry relative differences on personnel costs, we show the impact that benefits budgets have on total personnel budgets in percentages. For this, we use official data regarding the average salary per economic sector from Romania National Institute of Statistics and illustrate the differences in Figure 2. “Average gross salary per industries in 2021, in RON”. We can see that in the segments of IT and financial services the gross salary is almost double than in sectors like retail or industry.

Figure 1. Benefits budget sector variations from average per industry in 2021.

Figure 2. Average gross salary per industries in 2021, in RON.

In economic sectors with a lower average of gross salaries, the impact of extra-salary benefits plays a more important role. We will illustrate the impact of benefits costs on total personnel costs in Figure 3. "Cost impact relative to salary" costs. The impact is presented in percentages of benefits costs on the personnel costs.

We observe that the field of services affords the greatest ratio benefits budget versus total personnel costs. As a general trendline, while the differences on benefits budgets between sectors are relatively reduced, great differences appear on gross salaries between sectors. As a mention we could consider following statement: the lower the average salary, the more important the benefit package.

Figure 3. Cost impact of benefits package relative to salary costs (2021)

Another interesting phenomenon appears when we study the appreciation of certain categories of benefits by different age-groups. Figure 4. “Employees preferred benefits based on age-groups”. In this figure, we have three different age groups, “Junior” with under twenty-five years, “Mid” who represents all the employees in the range of twenty-five and forty, and “Senior” representing all employees over forty. On the other hand, we have three segments of benefits. The first one represents products, gifts, general items, which by being obtained as “benefits” do not need to be bought from the “personal budget”. The second segment is represented by experience. Here, the budget is spent for: holiday vouchers, travel or participating at different events. The third segment is represented by health insurance, access to medical treatment or contribution to private pension funds. The preferences of the active employees are for the younger generation in favor of objects or gifts, the middle generation is more balanced between gifts and personal experience, while the senior segment prefers personal experience and a greater concern on health and safety.

Figure 4. Employees preferred benefits based on age-groups.

Discussion and conclusions

As our first conclusion, a well-adapted policy of benefits can lower the personnel fluctuation through a greater employee satisfaction rate, while optimizing the company costs. In contrast, an inflexible set of poorly selected benefits can cause a great amount of unproductive costs for the company. For example, the compensation of dental services at a certain dental office was not at all appreciated by employees.

The mastery of the so-called benefits that fit the employees' expectations can make a great difference. In the ideal case, a flexible platform of benefits, that allows all single employees and employers to choose the desired benefits will eliminate wasted budgets and ensure a greater positive impact of the benefits. Electing the benefits can also represent a great chance to involve the employees to achieve a greater engagement rate.

A second conclusion would be that the industries with a lower salary average have a greater interest on benefit packages, since the total impact on personnel expenses has a higher proportion. If in some sectors, certain packages of benefits are considered as elementary conditions, in other segments, the benefits package can still be a differentiator from the competition.

Our third conclusion is that with time, the preferences of how to spend budgets change with age. If younger generation appreciates mostly shiny gifts and products, the older generation appreciates a lot more the personal experiences and investment in health and safety.

Notes

While analyzing the extra-salary benefits, we only consider those benefits accessible to all the employees of the organization. We did not take into consideration special benefits for management or certain categories of key persons. Also, we do not include financial bonus-systems dependent on individual or team performance nor bonus-systems based on the loyalty to the company.

Other common-sense HR practices, like individual performance evaluation, career planning and promotion possibilities were also not taken as benefits, even though, certain companies present them as such.

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